

Supplementary Material S2. Maximum Likelihood (ML) analyses of datasets variably including 15 mitochondrial genes (13 protein-coding genes (PCGs), 12S and 16S) and two nuclear genes (18S and 28S) via IQ-TREE. Numbers above branches are ML ultrafast bootstrap values; red circles at nodes indicate BS = 100. Outgroup is removed for ease of reading; see Supplementary Table S2 (available on Dryad) for specimen details. Branches incongruent with BEAST analysis (Fig. 1) marked in red.

